

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF *STREPTOGONOPUS PHIPSONI* (MILLIPEDES).
PART II. SOME CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF
THE FATTY MATTER

By RAFAT HUSAIN SIDDIQUI AND SYED MAQSUD ALI

The excellent researches of Klenk, Tsujimoto, Hilditch, Collin and others (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1933, 221, 67, 259, 264; *J. Soc. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1920, 23, 41, 1099; *Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 227; 1938, 32, 681; 1933, 27, 1373) on Depot fats of *Amphibia*, *Reptilia* and *Insecta* have not only elucidated the composition of the saturated and unsaturated acids of the fatty matter but have also shown the specific compositional differences that exist in the fats of aquatic and terrestrial animals. Considering the vast animal life our knowledge in this domain of science even now is extremely meagre.

The millipedes attracted the attention of the authors during a rainy season when they were collected and subjected to a chemical examination and as a result of this in part I of this series indication was given of a fatty matter and of a proteinous substance. Dimethylglyoxime was identified and isolated from the ether-soluble fraction of the alcoholic extract of the worms. In September, 1943, some more worms were collected mostly from the new breed and were extracted with ether. The orange ethereal solution was washed with a little water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and on removal of the solvent yielded a red oil giving the nauseating odour of the worms. The oil was kept away from light and was examined in January, 1944. The fat on titration with sodium hydroxide solution gave a high value for free acids and this may be due to its keeping for such a long time. The acetyl value was also high. The iodine value is an index of low unsaturation while the low Reichert-Meissl and Polenski values indicate a small amount of glycerides of volatile acids. The constants are given below (Table I).

TABLE I

Physical and chemical constants.

Smell	...	Peculiar nauseating odour of the worms	Iodine value	30·8; 31·4
Colour	...	Orange or ruby-red	Acid value	75·09
Specific gravity at 21°		0·9189	Reichert-Meissl value	1·21
Refractive index at 21°		1·46848	Polenski value	0·4
Saponification value		121·3; 123·6	Unsaponifiable matter	8·73

Future work will establish the nature and the composition of the saturated and unsaturated acids and also their relationship and importance with reference to the herbivorous habit of the worms.